

HUMAN RIGHTS AND SOCIAL ETHICS ISSUES IN THE “VIDEVDAT” BOOK

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One of the compositional parts of the Zoroastrian holy book, Avesta, is the Videvdat (“Law against the Daevas”, or “Demons”). It is one of the fully preserved texts of the Avesta and illuminates the religious, mythological, political, and legal systems, human rights, and social ethics issues of the ancient states of Iran and Central Asia. The book of Videvdat is a valuable source, not only as a historical and literary monument but also as a monument of religious and legal thought¹.

Firstly, if we look back at the history of civil society, the initial concepts concerning it were mentioned in Aristotle’s work, Politics². According to him, the human right to live freely must be ensured through the organization of human society based on justice and the rule of law. Special attention is paid to laws being correct and just in the governance of society. These ideas developed widely by the 17- th century and were perfected in the works of T.Hobbes³. The concept of civil society began to spread widely with the proclamation of the Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen during the Great French Revolution in the 18-th century. This is because the term “citizen” emerged among all equal members of society, and they began to recognize their personal interests tied to the interests of society and the state⁴. The ideas put forward by philosophers such as Kant, Rousseau, Hegel, and Popper began to reveal new facets of civil society and its essence as a universal human value⁵.

Specifically, the “Videvdat” discusses the place of a person in society and the need to strictly observe the established laws and rules of that society. In particular, the 4-th fragard of the “Videvdat” discusses actions arising from the breach of agreements, contracts, and their terms, and the application of penalty norms against them. At first glance, its content seems like a reaction to the daily events of social life. Yet, it strictly dictates that once a person recognizes the Truth and believes (in God), they must never turn back from this path and must not

¹ Avesta: Videvdat kitobi / M. Is’hoqov tarjimasi. – Toshkent: ToshDSHI, 2007.

² <https://ru.wikisum.org>.

³ Гоббс Т. Философские основания учения о гражданине. – Мн.: Харвест, М.: АСТ, 2001. – 304 с.

⁴ Гоббс Т. О гражданине // Гоббс Т. Избранные произведения. В 2 т. – М.: Мысль, 1964. – Т.1. – С. 287- 409. Гоббс Т. Левиафан, или Материя, форма и власть государства церковного и гражданского. – М.: Мысль, 2001. – 478 с.

⁵ Makhmudova G. About native land of zoroastrianism and Avesta. USA., Kontinent, 2008. - 93 p.;

renounce the word given before God. Breaking a promise was considered equivalent to renouncing the religion and faith. Such socio-ethical concepts could be applied to agreements and contracts in every daily matter of human life. The simplest level of contract violation was assessed as a sin equivalent to breaking the covenant between God and people. This is tantamount to saying that there is no difference between a major and a minor sin⁶.

We can see the following sentences concerning this issue in the “Videvdat”: Failing to return a borrowed debt is stealing a person’s property. A person who keeps a neighbor’s property (thing) in their home for any period is like someone who continuously steals the property of others day and night for that duration.

Agreements and their terms are illuminated in more detail in the dialogues between Zoroaster and Ahura-Mazda.

The following types of agreements were established by Ahura-Mazda:

The first is agreeing by giving one’s word.

The second is coming to terms by shaking hands.

The third is agreeing by setting a sheep (ewe) as collateral.

The fourth is setting a bull (ox) as collateral.

The fifth is agreeing by setting a person as collateral.

The sixth is agreeing by setting a fertile field as collateral⁷.

The first type of agreement is strictly confirmed by word. If this agreement is to be annulled (by the will of both parties), the parties agree by shaking hands.

The second type of agreement is concluded by shaking hands. To annul this agreement, a sheep is set as collateral. The third type of agreement is concluded by setting a sheep as collateral, which, to be annulled, requires an ox (bull) to be set as security (collateral).

The fourth type of agreement is concluded by setting an ox as collateral. Annulment of this agreement is only possible if a person is set as collateral. This final agreement, in turn, can only be annulled when a field (cultivated land) is set as collateral, and so on⁸.

In conclusion, as emphasized in these fragards, people strictly adhered to the law. If they failed to comply, they were subject to punishment and fines. Social and ethical qualities, such as the necessity for people to fulfill their promises to one another, were strongly emphasized..

⁶ Urazova R.T. Scientific Analysis Of Wicked Expressions In The Avesta. Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI) Volume 6, July, 2021. – P. 6666 -6671.

Avesta: Videvdat kitobi / M.Is’hoqov tarjimasasi. – Toshkent: ToshDSHI, 2007. – P.29-30.

⁸ Avesta: Videvdat kitobi / M.Is’hoqov tarjimasasi. – Toshkent: ToshDSHI, 2007. – P.31.

References:

1. Iskhakov M. (2007). Avesta: the Videvdat book. Tashkent, Tashkent Oriental
2. Гоббс Т. Философские основания учения о гражданине. – Мн.: Харвест, М.: АСТ, 2001. – 304 с.
3. Гоббс Т. О гражданине // Гоббс Т. Избранные произведения. В 2 т. – М.: Мысль, 1964. – Т.1. – С. 287-409.
4. Гоббс Т. Левиафан, или Материя, форма и власть государства церковного и гражданского. – М.: Мысль, 2001. – 478 с.
5. Makhmudova G. About native land of zoroastrianizm and Avesta. USA, Kontinent, 2008. - 93 p.;
6. Urazova R.T. Scientific Analysis Of Wicked Expressions In The Avesta. Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI) Volume 6, July, 2021. – P. 6666 – 6671.
7. <https://ru.wikisum.org>.

